

Wideband Near-field Extension for the 3GPP Geometry Based Stochastic Channel Model

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Abstract—Traditional radio channel models, including the 3GPP model, primarily assume far-field conditions where the plane wave approximation is valid. However, the increasing electrical size of antenna arrays, shorter communication distances, and the adoption of higher frequency bands with wider bandwidths necessitate accurate modeling of near-field propagation effects. This report presents an initial extension to the 3GPP geometry-based stochastic channel model to incorporate near-field wave propagation using a spherical wavefront approach. The proposed model accounts for near-field effects in both line-of-sight (LoS) and non-line-of-sight (NLoS) paths, introducing modifications that enable accurate representation of frequency-dependent phase variations and beam squint effects. A novel method based on virtual image theory is introduced to determine propagation distances for specular reflections, while a stochastic approach is employed to characterize scattered multipaths. The modified channel model maintains consistency with existing 3GPP frameworks while improving physical accuracy in the Fresnel region, thus providing a more realistic framework for evaluating next-generation wireless communication systems operating in the near-field regime.

I. INTRODUCTION

In wireless communication, the space around an antenna is divided into (i) the reactive near-field, (ii) the radiating near-field (Fresnel region), and (iii) the far-field. In the reactive near-field, energy is partially reflected, and field properties depend on distance, with the boundary defined as $d \leq 0.62\sqrt{D^3/\lambda}$ [1]. The Fresnel region supports fully radiated fields that follow a spherical wavefront, extending up to the Fraunhofer distance $d_F = 2D^2/\lambda$. In the far-field, the field stabilizes and behaves as a plane wave. For antenna arrays, the Fraunhofer distance is given by $d_{FA} = 2L_A^2/\lambda$ [2]. Fig. 1 illustrates the Fraunhofer distance as a function of array size and operating frequency. It is, therefore, evident, that, at high frequencies and large arrays, the Fresnel region typically dominates wireless propagation and thus needs to be accounted for in existing channel models.

A. Motivation & Contributions

In widely used geometry-based MIMO models, such as 3GPP TR38.901 [3], propagation paths (clusters or rays) are defined by their departure and arrival angles. Path lengths are specified through a delay parameter measured in time units, typically determined by the path angles, along with the direction of travel and speed of either the Tx or Rx. Additionally, antenna arrays are described by the relative

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Fig. 1. Fraunhofer array distance.

positions of their elements and the radiation patterns of individual elements. These element patterns are generally modeled without accounting for frequency-dependent variations across the considered bandwidth (BW).

The described approach neglects the frequency dependency of phase offsets between array elements, treating them uniformly across all frequencies within the bandwidth as if they correspond to the center frequency. In other words, variations in the electrical distance between array elements across the studied band are not accounted for.

One might question whether the aforementioned issues have any significant impact, particularly when the relative bandwidths are only a few percent of the center frequency. Potential shortcomings of the legacy modeling approach are identified and summarized in [4], including the reliance on planar wave modeling and the omission of the beam squinting effect. Frequency-dependent phase variations may influence beamforming performance, especially when the bandwidth and array dimensions are relatively large. While the current modeling approach has been effective for legacy systems, its impact is typically negligible in the main beam direction. However, phase sensitivity becomes critical when steering notches or nulling specific directions, as even small phase changes can significantly affect the depth of a null. For the study, development, and simulation of such systems, it is crucial that the channel model avoids introducing uncertainty or “non-physical” radio channel transfer functions.

This report proposes updates to enhance the physical accuracy of the legacy channel modeling approach outlined in 3GPP TR 38.901 and to address limitations associated with prior assumptions, including confined array sizes, relatively narrow bandwidths, and link distances adhering to the far-field condition. Specifically, this work aims to address the following deficiencies in the 3GPP model: 1) the absence of spherical wavefronts, and 2) the lack of support for the beam squint

effect.

The objective of this report is to introduce a straightforward modification to the legacy modeling approach, enhancing its physical accuracy and addressing several limitations associated with earlier assumptions, such as restricted array sizes, relatively narrow bandwidths, and link distances adhering to the far-field condition. While the 3GPP specification [3] mentions an optional modeling method for large bandwidths and arrays, the mentioned approach remains incomplete. The proposed solution aims to provide a simple method for determining the propagation distance between each Tx and Rx antenna element using the path parameters defined by the original model. Once the Tx-Rx antenna element distances along the path trajectories are obtained, calculating the MIMO channel coefficients becomes straightforward, enabling the incorporation of spherical wavefronts in a consistent manner.

Determining Tx-Rx distances can be categorized into three cases: 1) Line-of-Sight (LoS), which is straightforward; 2) scattering or diffraction, primarily occurring at lower frequencies like FR3; and 3) specular reflection, assumed to be the dominant interaction at sub-THz frequencies. For the LoS path, the distances between each Tx element and each Rx element can be calculated directly since the antenna coordinates and array geometries are explicitly defined in the model.

Non-Line-of-Sight (NLoS) paths resulting from specular reflection require a different approach, as the wave spreading (curvature) remains unchanged during such interactions. Conventional statistical multipath models, like QuaDRiGA [5] and 3GPP, represent each path as a plane wave characterized by gain, delay, and arrival and departure directions. With this standard Plane Wave Approximation (PWA), the MIMO channel response can be computed for arbitrary Tx and Rx array geometries [6]. However, the PWA becomes invalid when the Tx-Rx separation falls below the Rayleigh distance (i.e., in the near-field), where the curvature of wavefronts becomes significant. While spherical wave models for single LoS path channels are well-established [7], there are currently limited techniques for modeling them in NLoS multipath scenarios.

The modification proposed in this work aims to accurately capture the full spherical nature of each wavefront while being applicable to both LoS and NLoS paths resulting from an arbitrary number of specular reflections and scattering.

II. THE 3GPP SPATIAL CHANNEL MODEL

In 3GPP TR 38.901, the radio channel between transmit and receive antenna arrays at a given radio frequency f is represented as a matrix $H(f)$ with dimensions $M \times N$, given by

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{H}(f) &= \mathbf{H}_L(f) + \mathbf{H}_I(f) \\ &= (\mathbf{G}_{rx}(f, \Omega_L^{rx}) \mathbf{h}_L \mathbf{G}_{tx}(f, \Omega_L^{tx})^T) \odot \exp(-j2\pi f \tau_L) \\ &\quad + \sum_{l=1}^{L_s} \mathbf{G}_{rx}(f, \Omega_l^{rx}) \mathbf{h}_l \mathbf{G}_{tx}(f, \Omega_l^{tx})^T \odot \exp(-j2\pi f \tau_l) \end{aligned} \quad (1)$$

where N and M correspond to the number of transmit and receive elements, \odot denotes the Hadamard product (element-wise matrix product) operator, and $h_{(\cdot)}$ is the polarimetric

propagation channel matrix between the transmitter (Tx) location and the receiver (Rx) given by

$$\mathbf{h}_{(\cdot)} = \begin{bmatrix} p_{(\cdot)}^{\theta\theta} & p_{(\cdot)}^{\theta\phi} \\ p_{(\cdot)}^{\phi\theta} & p_{(\cdot)}^{\phi\phi} \end{bmatrix} \quad (2)$$

with scalars $p_{(\cdot)}^{xy}$, $x, y \in \{\theta, \phi\}$, denoting the complex channel gains related to a given path for received and transmitted polarization. In addition to the complex 2×2 coefficient matrix, each path is characterized by departure angle $\Omega_{(\cdot)}^{tx} = [\theta_{(\cdot)}^{tx}, \phi_{(\cdot)}^{tx}]$, arrival angle $\Omega_{(\cdot)}^{rx} = [\theta_{(\cdot)}^{rx}, \phi_{(\cdot)}^{rx}]$ and propagation delay $\tau_{(\cdot)}$. The double directional propagation channel for the Line-of-sight (LoS), and non Line-of-sight (NLoS) paths can then be written as

$$\begin{aligned} &\mathbf{h}(\Omega^{rx}, \Omega^{tx}, \tau) \\ &= \mathbf{h}_L(\Omega_L^{rx}, \Omega_L^{tx}, \tau_L) + \mathbf{h}_I(\Omega_I^{rx}, \Omega_I^{tx}, \tau_I) \\ &= \mathbf{h}_L \delta(\Omega^{rx} - \Omega_L^{rx}) \delta(\Omega^{tx} - \Omega_L^{tx}) \delta(\tau - \tau_L) \\ &\quad + \sum_{l=1}^{L_s} \mathbf{h}_l \delta(\Omega^{rx} - \Omega_l^{rx}) \delta(\Omega^{tx} - \Omega_l^{tx}) \delta(\tau - \tau_l) \end{aligned} \quad (3)$$

where L_s are the number of scattered paths with $\Omega_{(\cdot)}^{tx}$, $\Omega_{(\cdot)}^{rx}$ and $\tau_{(\cdot)}$ being the corresponding angle-of-departure, angle-of-arrival and delay respectively. The polarimetric antenna pattern matrices of Rx and Tx array are $\mathbf{G}_{rx}(f, \Omega_{(\cdot)}^{rx}) \in \mathbb{C}^{M \times 2}$ and $\mathbf{G}_{tx}(f, \Omega_{(\cdot)}^{tx}) \in \mathbb{C}^{N \times 2}$, respectively. Rows of $\mathbf{G}_{rx}(f, \Omega_{(\cdot)}^{rx})$ contain complex antenna gains g_m^θ and g_m^ϕ for polarizations θ and ϕ on the first and second column, respectively, at frequency f and arrival direction $\Omega_{(\cdot)}^{rx}$. Note that each antenna element pattern is defined with respect to its individual radiation phase centre.

In the Fresnel region, the plane wave approximation used above is no longer valid and a spherical wavefront should be considered instead. To this end, suitable modifications to the above model are proposed below.

III. EXTENSIONS TO THE 3GPP SPATIAL CHANNEL MODEL

Assuming that the interactions in the propagation environment are not frequency-dependent within the frequency band of interest, the polarimetric propagation channel matrix between the transmitter (Tx) location and the receiver (Rx) location is represented as

$$\mathbf{h}_{(\cdot)} = \begin{bmatrix} p_{(\cdot)}^{\theta\theta} & p_{(\cdot)}^{\theta\phi} \\ p_{(\cdot)}^{\phi\theta} & p_{(\cdot)}^{\phi\phi} \end{bmatrix} \quad (4)$$

where scalars $p_{(\cdot)}^{xy}$, $x, y \in \{\theta, \phi\}$, denote complex channel gains related to a given path and interaction type for received polarization and transmitted polarization. In addition to the complex 2×2 coefficient matrix, each path is characterized by departure angle $\Omega_{(\cdot)}^{tx} = [\theta_{(\cdot)}^{tx}, \phi_{(\cdot)}^{tx}]$, arrival angle $\Omega_{(\cdot)}^{rx} = [\theta_{(\cdot)}^{rx}, \phi_{(\cdot)}^{rx}]$ and propagation delay $\tau_{(\cdot)}$. The double directional propagation

channel for the Line-of-sight (LoS), reflected and scattered paths can then be written as

$$\begin{aligned}
& \mathbf{h}(\Omega^{rx}, \Omega^{tx}, \tau) \\
&= \mathbf{h}_L(\Omega_L^{rx}, \Omega_L^{tx}, \tau_L) + \mathbf{h}_r(\Omega_r^{rx}, \Omega_r^{tx}, \tau_r) + \mathbf{h}_s(\Omega_s^{rx}, \Omega_s^{tx}, \tau_s) \\
&= \mathbf{h}_L \delta(\Omega^{rx} - \Omega_L^{rx}) \delta(\Omega^{tx} - \Omega_L^{tx}) \delta(\tau - \tau_L) \\
&+ \sum_{l_r=1}^{L_r} \mathbf{h}_{l_r} \delta(\Omega^{rx} - \Omega_{l_r}^{rx}) \delta(\Omega^{tx} - \Omega_{l_r}^{tx}) \delta(\tau - \tau_{l_r}) \\
&+ \sum_{l_s=1}^{L_s} \mathbf{h}_{l_s} \delta(\Omega^{rx} - \Omega_{l_s}^{rx}) \delta(\Omega^{tx} - \Omega_{l_s}^{tx}) \delta(\tau - \tau_{l_s})
\end{aligned} \quad (5)$$

where L_r and L_s are the number of paths that undergo specular reflection and scattering with $\Omega_{(\cdot)}^{rx}$, $\Omega_{(\cdot)}^{tx}$ and $\tau_{(\cdot)}$ being the corresponding angle-of-departure, angle-of-arrival and delay respectively. Subsequently, the propagation pattern of antenna arrays is added to obtain the radio channel response. As before, it is assumed that the Tx and Rx antenna arrays have N and M elements respectively. The position of each Rx antenna $m = 1, \dots, M$ is defined by vector \mathbf{d}_m^{rx} in the same global geometry as the interaction points of the propagation paths. The Tx antenna pattern $\mathbf{G}_{tx}(f, \Omega^{tx}) \in \mathbb{C}^{N \times 2}$ and position vectors \mathbf{d}_n^{tx} are defined analogously.

A. Near-field Line-of-Sight Modeling

For LoS, each Tx/Rx antenna pair has a unique propagation delay for each path, determined simply as

$$\tau_{mn}^L = \frac{\|\mathbf{d}_m^{rx} - \mathbf{d}_n^{tx}\|}{c_0} = \frac{d_{mn}^L}{c_0} \quad (6)$$

where $\|\cdot\|$ denotes the Euclidean norm, c_0 is the speed of light in vacuum, and d_{mn}^L is the LoS distance between m -th Rx antenna to n -th Tx antenna. Accordingly, the divergence factor for LoS propagation can be defined as

$$F_{m,n}^{sc} = \frac{1}{s_{in}} \quad (7)$$

where s_{in} is the length of the LoS path segment from Tx to the next node in meters. Propagation delays of the LoS path can be collected in a matrix as

$$\mathbf{T}_L = \begin{bmatrix} \tau_{11}^L & \cdots & \tau_{1N}^L \\ \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ \tau_{M1}^L & \cdots & \tau_{MN}^L \end{bmatrix} \in \mathbb{C}^{M \times N} \quad (8)$$

Combining the propagation delays for all the N transmit and M receive antennas respectively, we can define the nearfield LoS MIMO radio channel $\mathbf{H}_L(f) \in \mathbb{C}^{M \times N}$ in the frequency domain as

$$\mathbf{H}_L(f) = (\mathbf{G}_{rx}(f, \Omega_L^{rx}) \mathbf{h}_L \mathbf{G}_{tx}(f, \Omega_L^{tx})^T) \odot \exp(-j2\pi f \mathbf{T}_L) \quad (9)$$

It is important to note that if the distance continues to grow, the near-field MIMO channel model will ultimately simplify into its equivalent far-field counterpart in (1).

B. Near-field Modeling for Specular Paths

In real-world scenarios, the propagation distances for individual antenna elements in both the Tx and Rx arrays on a line-of-sight (LoS) path vary slightly. These path lengths differ based on the specific geometry and orientation of each array. For non-line-of-sight (NLoS) paths, the propagation distances vary further, influenced not only by geometry and orientation but also by the type of interaction and location of the object causing the interaction. These slight variations in path length introduce frequency-dependent phase offsets across the signals received by each antenna element. This occurs because a fixed distance in meters translates to different wavelength counts at different frequencies.

The objective of the subsequent section is to offer a straightforward approach for calculating the propagation distance between each Tx and Rx antenna element under specular reflection. For mobile channels, this involves determining time-variant propagation delays for each antenna pair. These per-element propagation delays can replace the phase terms associated with departure/arrival angles in antenna arrays, as used in conventional models like (1). For the LoS path, calculating distances between Tx and Rx arrays is direct, given the known positions of both the arrays and their individual elements. However, for NLoS paths, this calculation becomes challenging because the model specifies only angles and delay, without providing the locations or characteristics of interacting objects. If information about the position and orientation of, for example, a reflecting surface or a diffracting edge were available, we could accurately determine per-element path lengths, but such details are not included in the model.

To address this issue, we can employ a method of determining virtual array positions for each propagation path. This involves rotating the Tx antenna array in the global Cartesian coordinate system so that the departure and arrival angles align, with the distance between the array centers matching the original path length in meters. Using the original Rx antenna coordinates and the newly established virtual Tx antenna coordinates, we can then compute the distances for each antenna element as we would in the LoS case. This procedure is applied independently for each path. The underlying assumption is that the interaction type is reflection, as this is the most prevalent and highest-gain interaction at sub-THz frequencies. In cases where no specific interaction type is provided for NLoS paths at high frequencies, we can assume they are specular reflections. The near-field impact on specular reflection is introduced by modifying τ_{l_r} based on the first and last bounce points. The unit vectors of $\mathbf{r}_{l_r}^{tx}$ and $\mathbf{r}_{l_r}^{rx}$ pointing to the coordinates of these interaction are expressed as

$$\mathbf{r}_l = [\sin \theta_l \cos \phi_l, \sin \theta_l \sin \phi_l, \cos \theta_l]^T \quad (10)$$

In higher frequencies, the dominant multipaths will be mostly originated from specular reflection. Thus, the method of images is used to add the spherical wavefront behavior of the reflected multipaths to the model. We define the following auxiliary parameters to specify the position vectors of the array

Fig. 2. Illustration of the proposed method of images with a ULA in which the transmit antenna position is changed relative to the AoA and AoD of a specific specular path.

centres in the global coordinate system as follows

$$\mathbf{d}^{rx} = \frac{1}{M} \sum_m \mathbf{d}_m^{rx}, \quad \mathbf{d}^{tx} = \frac{1}{N} \sum_m \mathbf{d}_m^{tx} \quad (11)$$

First, define a rotation matrix $\mathbf{R}_{l_r} \in \mathbb{R}^{3 \times 3}$ for each specular path l_r , based on the arrival unit vector $\mathbf{r}_{l_r}^{rx}$ from angle $\Omega_{l_r}^{rx}$ and the departure unit vector $\mathbf{r}_{l_r}^{tx}$ towards angle $\Omega_{l_r}^{tx}$, as follows:

$$\mathbf{R}_{l_r} = \mathbf{I} + 2\mathbf{K}^2 = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 & 1 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix} + 2 \begin{bmatrix} 0 & -a_z & a_y \\ a_z & 0 & -a_x \\ -a_y & a_x & 0 \end{bmatrix} \quad (12)$$

where \mathbf{I} is the 3×3 identity matrix and \mathbf{a} is the unit vector pointing between $-\mathbf{r}_{l_r}^{rx}$ and $\mathbf{r}_{l_r}^{tx}$ in the plane set by them and given as

$$\mathbf{a} = [a_x \ a_y \ a_z]^T = \frac{-\mathbf{r}_{l_r}^{rx} + \mathbf{r}_{l_r}^{tx}}{\|-\mathbf{r}_{l_r}^{rx} + \mathbf{r}_{l_r}^{tx}\|} \quad (13)$$

For the l_r -th specular path, the Tx antenna elements are rotated using \mathbf{R}_{l_r} so that the new virtual positions and orientations of the antenna elements satisfy the condition where the propagation distance between the array centers is $\tau_{l_r} c_0$, with the arrival and departure vectors aligned towards each other, as shown in the example in Fig. 2. The position vector for the n -th virtual Tx element for the l_r -th specular path is then given by

$$\mathbf{d}_{l_r n}^{vtx} = \mathbf{R}_{l_r}(\mathbf{d}_n^{tx} - \mathbf{d}^{tx}) + \mathbf{d}^{rx} + \mathbf{r}_{l_r}^{rx} \tau_{l_r} c_0 \quad (14)$$

In equation (14), the n -th element is first translated near the origin so that the array center is positioned exactly at the origin. It is then rotated by \mathbf{R}_{l_r} , followed by a translation to the position specified by the Rx center. Finally, it is shifted in the direction of the arrival unit vector to a distance determined by τ_{l_r} .

The obtained geometry after the overall process is depicted in Fig. 2. Each Tx-Rx antenna pair now has a distinct propagation delay for each specular path, calculated as

$$\tau_{mn}^{l_r} = \frac{\|\mathbf{d}_m^{rx} - \mathbf{d}_{l_r n}^{vtx}\|}{c_0} = \frac{d_{mn}^{l_r}}{c_0} \quad (15)$$

Fig. 3. Illustration of the virtual Tx generation under multiple specular reflections.

The propagation delays for l_r -th specular path can now be organized into a matrix as follows

$$\mathbf{T}_{l_r} = \begin{bmatrix} \tau_{11}^{l_r} & \cdots & \tau_{1N}^{l_r} \\ & \ddots & \\ \tau_{M1}^{l_r} & \cdots & \tau_{MN}^{l_r} \end{bmatrix} \in \mathbb{R}_+^{M \times N} \quad (16)$$

Finally, incorporating the Tx and Rx antenna arrays with N and M elements, respectively, allows us to define the specular MIMO radio channel $\mathbf{H}_r(f) \in \mathbb{C}^{M \times N}$ in the frequency domain as

$$\mathbf{H}_r(f) = \sum_{l_r=1}^{L_r} \mathbf{G}_{rx}(f, \Omega_{l_r}^{rx}) \mathbf{h}_{l_r} \mathbf{G}_{tx}(f, \Omega_{l_r}^{tx})^T \odot \exp(-j2\pi f \mathbf{T}_{l_r}) \quad (17)$$

1) *Generalization of the proposed modification for arbitrary number of specular reflections:* The method of images proposed above is fairly general in nature and applicable to NLoS paths undergoing multiple specular reflections [8] as is illustrated below using the following two observations related to reflection based wave propagation.

The first observation relates to the illustration in Fig. 3, where the Tx, Rx, and three obstacles cause three successive specular reflections. The orientation and direction of departure (DoD) of the Tx antenna array are depicted, with the spreading of the transmitted wave shown by solid blue lines representing the wave's opening angle. The virtual Tx, drawn using dashed red lines, maintains the same overall path length, spreading, direction of arrival (DoA), and relative DoD. This depiction is created using principles of image theory and basic euclidean geometry and achieves the same result as the procedure outlined in (12)-(14) above. The illustration conveys that virtual Tx positions and orientations can be determined regardless of the number of successive interactions. To achieve this, we translate the Tx array to a position indicated by the DoA vector, place it at a distance from the Rx corresponding to the propagation delay, and rotate the Tx array so that the DoD vector aligns with the Rx.

The second observation focuses on the principles of wave propagation and ray tracing. In a reflection interaction, the

divergence factor of a wave is proportional to the cumulative propagation distance, irrespective of the number of successive reflections. In other words, the wave's curvature remains unchanged when reflected off smooth planar surfaces. This is mathematically (albeit indirectly) represented, for example, in equations (6) and (17) of [8] which shows that the divergence factor for reflection is

$$F_{m,n}^{ref} = \frac{s_r}{s_{in} + s_r} \quad (18)$$

where where s_{in} is the cumulative distance from n -th Tx antenna to the reflection point and s_r is the distance from the reflection point to the next node.

Contrary to (18), the divergence factor for scattering is proportional to the distance from the scattering point to the receiver node thereby making the above modification inadmissible for scenarios where the underlying propagation mechanism is based on scattering. Notably, the divergence factor for scattering, can be expressed as [8]

$$F_{m,n}^{sc} = \frac{1}{s_s} \quad (19)$$

where s_s is the distance from the scattering point to the receiver node. Consequently, since $F_{m,n}^{sc}$ depends on the distance between the scatterer and the receiver, specifying the coordinates of the last-hop scatterers is sufficient to fully characterize the scattered multipaths between each scattering node and the corresponding Rx antenna. Furthermore, as noted in (7), the divergence of the LoS path between each Tx antenna and the first bounce scatterer, $F_{m,n}^{los}$, is similarly proportional to the path length between the antenna and the corresponding scattering node. By combining these divergence functions, it can be concluded that, unlike specular reflection, specifying the locations of both the first and last bounce scatterers is sufficient to completely characterize a scattered multipath between the m -th Tx antenna and the n -th Rx antenna.

For example, a path involving a single reflection has a divergence factor term given by the product of $F_{m,n}^{los}$, for the distance s_{in} from the n -th Tx antenna to the reflection point, and $F_{m,n}^{ref}$, which accounts for the distances s_{in} and s_r , where s_r is the distance from the reflection point to the m -th Rx antenna. Similarly, a path involving a single scattering has a divergence factor term given by the product of $F_{m,n}^{los}$ for the distance s_{in} from the n -th Tx antenna to the scattering point and $F_{m,n}^{sc}$ for the distance s_s from the scatterer to the m -th Rx antenna.

This insight is utilized below to model the scattered multipaths of the composite channel response defined in (5).

C. Near-field Modeling for Scattered Paths

To characterize spherical propagation of the scattered paths in the nearfield of an electrically large antenna array, we proceed as follows. The propagation paths in this case are characterized by not only by the gain, path length, and angles, but also the delay offsets caused by the first and last bounce interactions of the scatterers between the m -th receive and n -th transmit antennas. Let, $d_{l_s}^{tx}$ and $d_{l_s}^{rx}$ be the distance from the Tx and Rx array centers to the first-hop and last-hop

Fig. 4. Illustration of the nearfield geometry for scattering with a ULA.

scatterers respectively along the l_s -th path. Additionally, $\Delta\tau_{l_s n}^{tx}$ represents the delay offset caused by the difference between the distance from the first-hop scatterer to the n -th Tx antenna and the distance from the same scatterer to the Tx array center. $\Delta\tau_{l_s m}^{rx}$ represents a similar delay offset on the Rx side from the last-hop scatterer. Then, the delay offsets between the n -th Tx and m -th Rx antenna in the nearfield can be calculated as

$$\begin{aligned} \Delta\tau_{l_s n}^{tx} &= \frac{\|d_{l_s}^{tx} \mathbf{r}_{l_s}^{tx}\| - \|\mathbf{d}_n^{tx} - (\mathbf{d}^{tx} + d_{l_s}^{tx} \mathbf{r}_{l_s}^{tx})\|}{c_0} \\ \Delta\tau_{l_s m}^{rx} &= \frac{\|d_{l_s}^{rx} \mathbf{r}_{l_s}^{rx}\| - \|\mathbf{d}_m^{rx} - (\mathbf{d}^{rx} + d_{l_s}^{rx} \mathbf{r}_{l_s}^{rx})\|}{c_0} \end{aligned} \quad (20)$$

where the unit vectors $\mathbf{r}_{l_s}^{tx}$ and $\mathbf{r}_{l_s}^{rx}$ point to the coordinates of the first and last bounce scatterers respectively and are as defined in (120). It can be shown that for $d_{l_s}^{tx} \gg \|\mathbf{d}_n^{tx} - \mathbf{d}^{tx}\|$ and $d_{l_s}^{rx} \gg \|\mathbf{d}_m^{rx} - \mathbf{d}^{rx}\|$, the spherical wavefront can be approximated by a planar wavefront when $d_{l_s}^{tx}$ and $d_{l_s}^{rx}$ are larger than the corresponding Rayleigh distance $d_{FA} = 2L_A^2/\lambda$, where L_A represents the array's maximum physical dimension, and λ is the propagating wavelength.

The unique propagation delays between the N transmit and M receive antennas for the l_s -th path can be expressed in the form of a matrix as

$$\mathbf{T}_{l_s} = \tau_{l_s} + \begin{bmatrix} \Delta\tau_{l_s 1}^{tx} + \Delta\tau_{l_s 1}^{rx} & \cdots & \Delta\tau_{l_s N}^{tx} + \Delta\tau_{l_s 1}^{rx} \\ & \ddots & \\ \Delta\tau_{l_s 1}^{tx} + \Delta\tau_{l_s M}^{rx} & \cdots & \Delta\tau_{l_s N}^{tx} + \Delta\tau_{l_s M}^{rx} \end{bmatrix} \quad (21)$$

Incorporating Tx and Rx antenna arrays with N and M elements, respectively, the scattered MIMO radio channel in the frequency domain can be defined as

$$\mathbf{H}_s(f) = \sum_{l_s=1}^{L_s} \mathbf{G}_{rx}(f, \Omega_{l_s}^{rx}) \mathbf{h}_{l_s} \mathbf{G}_{tx}(f, \Omega_{l_s}^{tx})^T \odot \exp(-j2\pi f \mathbf{T}_{l_s}) \quad (22)$$

The position $\mathbf{s}_{l_s}^\alpha$ of the scatterer involved in the first hop can be calculated by using $d_{l_s}^{tx}$ as

$$\mathbf{s}_{l_s}^\alpha = \mathbf{d}^{tx} + d_{l_s}^{tx} \mathbf{r}_{l_s}^{tx} \quad (23)$$

Similarly, the position $\mathbf{s}_{l_s}^\omega$ of the scatterer in the last hop of the l_s -th path can be calculated as

$$\mathbf{s}_{l_s}^\omega = \mathbf{d}^{rx} + d_{l_s}^{rx} \mathbf{r}_{l_s}^{rx} \quad (24)$$

To generate the near-field channel, we need to determine the distances $d_{l_s}^{tx}$ and $d_{l_s}^{rx}$ between the center of the transmit and

Fig. 5. Modified channel coefficient generation procedure.

receive array and the first and last scattering objects for each path l_s . Given that the 3GPP framework does not provide any explicit modeling of the scattering object, $d_{l_s}^{tx}$ and $d_{l_s}^{rx}$ can be chosen to be random variables whose distribution is derived from simple geometrical considerations. From the propagation delay, we can compute the propagation distance of the l_s -th path as $d_{l_s} = \tau_{l_s} c_0 + \|\mathbf{d}^{tx} - \mathbf{d}^{rx}\|$. Then, d_{l_s} represents an upper bound for determining $d_{l_s}^{tx}$ and $d_{l_s}^{rx}$ because the overall propagation delay is greater than or equal to the sum of lengths of the first and the last bounce paths i.e

$$d_{l_s}^{tx} + d_{l_s}^{rx} \leq d_{l_s} \quad (25)$$

where equality holds only for a single bounce multipath. With these considerations, $d_{l_s}^{tx}$ and $d_{l_s}^{rx}$ can be determined as follows:

- Compute the overall propagation distance for each path l_s as $d_{l_s} = \tau_{l_s} c_0 + \|\mathbf{d}^{tx} - \mathbf{d}^{rx}\|$.
- Draw $d_{l_s}^{tx} \sim \mathcal{U}(d_{l_s}^{min}, d_{l_s} - d_{l_s}^{min})$.
- Draw $d_{l_s}^{rx} \sim \mathcal{U}(d_{l_s}^{min}, d_{l_s} - d_{l_s}^{tx})$.

where $d_{l_s}^{min}$ is a parameter representing the minimum distance between the center of the transmit/receive array and the first/last bounce scatterer which should be set according to the propagation scenario.

To incorporate the modeling of spherical wavefronts, the existing 3GPP framework should be extended as shown in Fig.5 whereby additional steps, shown in green are needed for computing the delay offsets of the non-specular multipaths and the equivalent LoS delays of the specular multipaths.

IV. CONCLUSION

An extension to the 3GPP TR 38.901 channel model is proposed here to incorporate spherical wavefront modeling, improving the accuracy of wireless channel representation in the Fresnel region. Equations are developed to calculate the phase components of LoS and NLoS paths based on the distances between the transmit/receive arrays and the first/last bounce

scatterers, as well as the interactions experienced by each multipath. A novel image-based method is also introduced to compute the propagation distances of reflected multipaths in a physically consistent manner. Additionally, a stochastic approach is introduced for determining the distances to the first and last scatterers while maintaining physical consistency and the required modifications to the 3GPP channel generation procedure are subsequently outlined.

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

This work is funded by the Hexa-X-II project, receiving funding from the Smart Networks and Services Joint Undertaking (SNS JU) under the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No. 101095759.

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